

USE OF TRANSFORMATION IN THE DIRECTION OF DESIGN AND ITS IMPORTANCE

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Abstract. *In this article, information about transformation and its use in clothing design is highlighted.*

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We currently use many transformer buildings, products, things and household appliances. But it is impossible to find such information in the Uzbek language explained in the language of science. Transformation is used in all areas of design direction. For example, we can see that transformation is used to change the appearance of various buildings, to change their general shape in the field of architecture, in industrial design, dress design, in many different aspects of art.

Transformation (derived from the Latin word *transformatio*) is a change in the appearance, shape, and important properties of something. If we consider this term in the context of clothing design:

“Transformation is the property of changing the original forms and parameters of objects of the subject-spatial world in the process of existence or activity. Therefore, according to the definition directly related to the process of designing clothes and its elements, it can be concluded that transformations occur both during the wearing process with human participation and during the entire service life of the product. Changing its aesthetic and physical appearance). On the whole, it can be described as “a material structure that characterizes an object that can be changed, capable of taking on a number of different constructive and aesthetic states based on its "reconstruction"”. Therefore, convertible clothing is a movable material structure (design and aesthetic) that allows it to be transformed into different types of products or to significantly change the properties of these products.

Changes in clothing design are determined by the dynamics of actions performed by a person, the change of objects and elements of clothing or the change of shape during its use. Transformation can be done in two main ways.

- change one form to another;
- change the details to another form.

Considering the process of changing clothes from the point of view of economy, it should be noted that it will be convenient for both the consumer and the manufacturer. A consumer who buys a single product that can be changed, in fact receives several products that are the same in terms of color and style, material, but differ in functional, operational and ergonomic purposes. In addition to the economic aspect of designing these products, convertible clothing allows the consumer to enjoy a number of other positive functions.

After all, with the help of transformation in clothes, a person changes his personal appearance in a very short time, that is, without returning home, he can look suitable for a certain situation and situation in a certain time. Using a minimal set of variable products and clothing

items, the consumer has the opportunity to change his image. It should also be noted that the changeable products in the modern costume allow creating an individual image for a dynamic lifestyle associated with a certain frequency of changes in functional life processes, changes in various events.

For a long time, certain methods of constructive-technological and compositional solutions for changeable clothes and its elements have been developed. This information allows us to present the variety of different variations used in clothing. There is a classification of techniques and methods of changing clothing items and elements, which are basic information for designing modern changeable products for various functional, ergonomic and aesthetic purposes.

Combinative method - this is the process of combining forms and their elements in different ways or the search for an option, resulting in the creation of geometric, structural, color and other combinatory systems.

The modular method allows to create different forms at the expense of the module.

Ensuring its interchangeability implies structural, technological and functional completeness, and the module itself can be a finished product or an integral part of a product with other functional purposes.

The flat cutting method involves the use of fabrics of the material according to the principle of "positioning - folding" to create products of various assortments and shapes.

Kinetics - this is the creation of dynamics of forms, decoration, fabric patterns by using bright objects, LEDs, autonomous lighting, rotating or moving elements of the costume.

Changeable clothing gives the consumer the freedom to make decisions in the formation of a personal wardrobe, and can serve as an impetus for experimentation and improvisation in clothing. Changeable clothing allows the consumer to save time and money and extend the life of clothing. Through this, it allows us to eliminate existing environmental and economic problems, and at the same time, it will be used effectively to fill the wardrobe.

Taking this into account, the number of designers who create in this direction is increasing as the need for transformational clothes increases.

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